

The Use of Bali Aga Dialect in the Work Domain

Ni Ketut Veri Kusumaningrum¹, Ketut Artawa², I Made Suastra³, I Wayan Pastika⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Udayana University, Denpasar, Bali, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The Bali Aga dialect as a variant of the Balinese language spoken by the Bali Aga community in Tigawasa Village faces challenges of preservation in the era of modernization. The work domain is a crucial domain in daily language use that can reflect the vitality of a language or dialect. This research focuses on the preservation of the Bali Aga dialect in the work domain in Tigawasa Village which is one of the Bali Aga villages that still maintains traditions and ancestral languages. This research uses mixe method (quantitative qualitative) which is collected through observation, questionnaire and interview. A purposive sampling technique was used to select representative informants. This research uses Fishman's (1972) domain theory as the main framework, supported by Greenfield's (1968) theory and Parasher's (1980) theory. Parasher's theory, (1980). The results show that the preservation of Bali Aga dialect in the work domain in Tigawasa Village shows positive results with the intensity of the use of Bali Aga dialect in the work domain amounting to 70%. The Balinese Aga dialect tends to be better preserved in traditional work (informal sector), while the use of Indonesian language is more dominant in modern work (formal sector). The use of Bali Aga dialect in Tigawasa Village is influenced by several factors such as: the strength of cultural identity, the survival of traditional economic activities, and the ongoing intergenerational language transmission. The conclusion is that the preservation of the Bali Aga dialect in the work domain in Tigawasa Village shows a complex trend. Despite facing pressure from Indonesian language and modernization, this dialect still has strong vitality, especially in the context of traditional work and local interaction. However, revitalization efforts and supportive language policies are needed to ensure the sustainability of the Bali Aga dialect in the work domain, especially facing the challenges of globalization and socio-economic changes.

KEYWORDS: dialect, Balinese Aga, work domain, Tigawasa Village

I. INTRODUCTION

Balinese as one of the regional languages in Indonesia, has a variety of dialects spread across various regions on the island of Bali. One of the unique and interesting dialects to be studied is the Bali Aga dialect spoken by the Bali Aga people in several old villages in Bali. One of the villages that uses the Bali Aga dialect is Tigawasa Village which is located in Banjar District, Buleleng Regency. In the era of globalization and rapid modernization, many local dialects face the threat of extinction as well as the Bali Aga dialect. The existence of language shift symptoms in the Bali Aga dialect is a language phenomenon that needs to be studied. The symptoms of language shift also refer to data showing that in Indonesia in 2022 there were 25 endangered regional languages, 6 critical, and 11 languages declared extinct (Bali Province Language Center (2022). The increase in language extinction is seen to increase in 2023 with data on approximately 704 regional languages that are still alive and actively used and 14 regional languages that have become extinct (Ethnologue, 2023). Therefore, research on the preservation of the Bali Aga dialect, especially in the work domain in Tigawasa Village, Banjar District, Bali is important to do.

The preservation of Bali Aga dialect in this article focuses on the use of Bali Aga dialect in the work domain in Tigawasa Village. The work domain is one of the important domains in language use, as it includes significant social and professional interactions in the daily life of the people of Tigawasa Village. Furthermore, Gumperz (1982) emphasizes the role of the work domain as a place where social and linguistic identities interact and are negotiated through language choices. In line with Gumperz, Leanne Hinton (2001) also argues that the maintenance of minority language use in the work domain is key to the long-term sustainability of the language in the community. Examining the maintenance of the Bali Aga dialect in the work domain can provide an overview of the vitality and sustainability of the Bali Aga dialect in the community of Tigawasa Village.

This study aims to analyze the factors that influence the preservation of the Bali Aga dialect in the work domain, identify the challenges faced in the preservation efforts, and explore strategies that can be applied to maintain the sustainability of the dialect. The results of this study are expected to contribute to the preservation of regional languages and local wisdom, and become a reference for policy makers in formulating concrete steps to preserve the Bali Aga dialect.

II. THEORY

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The language domain theory applied to this research is the theory of Fishman, (1968), Greenfield's theory (1968) and Parasher's theory, (1980). According to Fishman (1968) the domain is the main indicator of language maintenance. Domains are defined as *institutional social contexts* in language use (Fishman, 1968). Fishman, (1968) explained that the domain refers to the selection or use of language that best suits the speaker's environment. In line with Fishman, Greenfield (1968) states that domain refers to social situations and activities that are consistently and universally associated with the use of a particular language. Meanwhile, according to Parasher, (1980) domain is a set of situations in language use.

Fishman (1968, 1972) suggests 4 domains namely: family sphere, neighbor sphere, work sphere, religion sphere. Then, Greenfield (1980) stated five domains, namely the domains of family, kinship, religion, education, and work. While Parasher (1980) states that there are seven domains, namely the domains of family, kinship, neighborliness, transactions, education, government, and work.

Fishman (1972) explained that the domain is related to the conditions in which an individual is required to choose language and certain topics of conversation in accordance with the socio-cultural norms of the speech community concerned. Based on this description, the domain is the context or social situation of speakers to choose the language used in communication, taking into account the factors of people (participants), the location of speech events, and the topic of conversation.

Domain is used to explain language use behavior in bilingual and multilingual societies to see patterns of language maintenance in society. Based on the domain, it can also be seen which language is always used in intragroup interaction and which language is always used for intergroup interaction.

By referring to the theory above, the domain refers to the situation of language use in a social context or setting that depends on the function and topic of conversation in a speech community. In this study, we will divide the domain into two, namely the conventional domain and the modern domain. The conventional domain consists of family domain, religion domain, neighbor domain, transaction domain. Meanwhile, the modern domain consists of the education domain, government domain, work domain and digital domain. This domain construction is used as the basic framework for domain analysis in this dissertation.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research uses *mixed* method. The data generated in the form of quantitative data in the form of percentages and descriptive data obtained from the speech of Balinese Aga dialect speakers in the work domain in Tigawasa Village. The location of this research is Tigawasa Village, Banjar District, Buleleng Regency, Bali Province. Data collection techniques in this research are observation, documentation, questionnaires and interviews. The object of this research is Bali Aga dialect speakers in the work domain. The analysis of work domain refers to Greenfield (1968), Fishman (1972), Parasher (1980). The work domain in Tigawasa Village includes activities in the formal and informal sectors such as weaving, farming and cattle breeding.

IV. FINDING AND DISCUSSION

The work domain in the use of Bali Aga dialect in Tigawasa Village refers to the context of using Bali Aga dialect in the work environment or in situations related to work activities in both formal and informal environments. The majority of people in Tigawasa Village work at home as bamboo weavers and gardeners. In the realm of work, the dominant community uses the Bali Aga dialect. However, for people who work in the village office or in schools and official institutions, they will use the Bali Aga dialect, the Bali Dataran dialect and Bahasa Indonesia. The following percentage of the use of the Bali Aga dialect in the work domain is presented in the form of a diagram.

Percentage Diagram of Bali Aga Dialect Usage in the Work Domain

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Diagram 5 shows the percentage of Bali Aga dialect usage in Tigawasa Village in the work domain is 70%. The 70% percentage shows that the Bali Aga dialect is still significantly used in the work context in Tigawasa Village. This is a fairly high figure for the work domain, given that this domain is often more open to the influence of outside languages. This percentage indicates that the Bali Aga dialect is still very relevant and functional in economic activities and daily work in Tigawasa Village. The following are examples of conversations in the work domain.

Data 1 Conversation in the work domain.

P1: *Kesit je buluhe Mang!*

(Split the bamboo Mang!)

P2: *Ken maluen kesit? Ane **dawa** what ane bawak?*

(Which one split first? The long one or the short one?)

P1: *Ane **dawa**, ya kal bin puan juange ken ne meli*

(The long one, the problem is that in two days it will be taken by the buyer) P2 : *Directly **pal-pal** or kesit **duang**?*

(Directly cleaned or split?)

P1: ***Kesit duang**, jepen me **mal pal**.*

(Just split it, I'll clean it later)

The above conversation occurs in the realm of work that takes place at home. The conversation takes place between two people, identified as P1 and P2, who are discussing the work of splitting and cleaning bamboo. The conversation took place in Balinese Aga Village dialect. The context of the work that occurs is the work done related to bamboo processing. M and K use the Bali Aga dialect consistently. The typical Bali Aga dialect words used are '*dawa, kesit, pal-pal, duang, mal pal*'. The word *dawa* (length) is an adjective that describes the size or dimension of an object. In the conversation above, it refers to bamboo. The characteristic of the word *dawa* is that at the end of the word it uses /a/ which is a characteristic of the Bali Aga dialect. The words *kesit* (sort/reduce), *pal-pal*, *mal pal* are typical words of the Bali Aga dialect in the process of working on crafts or woven bamboo. It refers to the stages from bamboo to plaiting. The word *duang* (alone) is a type of adverb. In the conversation above, it is used to emphasize the previous word.

The conversation above gives an idea of the dynamics of work in an informal context where communication is direct, decision-making is quick and involved with the situation and place. It is different in the realm of work that is located in the formal sector such as in the office, they also use Balinese dialect plains and Indonesian when communicating. Here is an example of the conversation.

Data 2 Conversation in the work domain.

D1: *Prinang je berkase to!*

(Print the file!)

D2 : ***Japa** file neh?*

(Where is the file?)

D1: *Mesimpen in Mr. Ketute's file*

(Saved in Mr. Ketut's file)

D2: *O ane ne, nah! double **horse** ma'am?*

(O this one, ok! how many copies ma'am?)

D1: *Duplicate 5 **duang**, kal diveng to the event section.*

(5 copies only, will be distributed to the event section)

D2: *Ok*

(ok)

The above conversation took place in the workplace at the village office, they (D1 and D2) communicated with Bali Dataran dialect, Indonesian language and Bali Aga dialect. The typical words of Bali Aga dialect are '*japa, kuda, duang*'. However, in the conversation

there are already Indonesian words such as *print, file, file, duplicate, event section, ok* in the sentences spoken. The work domain is still dominated by the use of Bali Aga dialect because the percentage of people who work in the formal sector is very small.

In the work domain there is also a distinctive lexicon associated with their work as bamboo weavers such as '*ngulat*' referring to the weaving process, '*muquin*' referring to the process of making a conical corner on a sokasi/keben. Sokasi or eben is a place to put Hindu ceremonial facilities. '*Mungain*' refers to the process of making the motif of the sokasi or eben. In addition to sokasi or eben weaving, the community also weaves '*bedeg*'. '*Bedeg*' is a bamboo weaving used for building materials, the size of the '*bedeg*' weaving is quite large. The lexicon in the weaving process is still used and still exists. The equivalent of the lexicon is very difficult to find in other languages because bamboo weaving is a characteristic of the Tigawasa Village community.

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Factors that influence language maintenance in Bali Aga dialect in Tigawasa Village are

- 1) The people of Tigawasa Village are always proud to use the Bali Aga dialect and consider it a symbol of identity and pride of the Tigawasa community.
- 2) The relatively remote location of Tigawasa Village helps minimize outside influences.
- 3) Strong bonds between community members encourage the continued use of the Bali Aga dialect.
- 4) The inheritance of the Bali Aga dialect from parents to children is still very high.
- 5) The community's occupation is still dominated by traditional work such as gardening, weaving, and animal husbandry which supports the daily use of the dialect.

The challenges faced in the preservation of the Bali Aga dialect language in Tigawasa Village are:

- 1) The influx of technology and media that generally use Indonesian or foreign languages.
- 2) The movement of people outside the village or the influx of newcomers.
- 3) The use of Indonesian as the language of instruction in the formal sector.
- 4) Increased interaction with tourists using national and international languages.
- 5) Perception that local dialects have less prestige than standard languages.

Responding to the challenges above, a strategy is needed to maintain the sustainability of the Bali Aga dialect in the future. These strategies are:

- 1) Recording and documenting the Bali Aga dialect systematically.
- 2) Integrating the Bali Aga dialect in the local curriculum.
- 3) Organizing festivals and events that promote the use of the Bali Aga dialect.
- 4) Creating village regulations that support the use of Bali Aga dialects in the work domain.
- 5) Develop digital media and digital content that collaborates Bali Aga dialects.
- 6) Involve universities and research institutes in Bali Aga dialect preservation efforts.
- 7) Encourage local businesses that use the Bali Aga dialect as an added value.
- 8) Campaign on the importance of maintaining the Bali Aga dialect as a cultural heritage.

By understanding the factors that influence language maintenance in the Bali Aga dialect, identifying challenges, and implementing appropriate strategies, efforts to maintain the Bali Aga dialect in the workplace in Tigawasa Village can be carried out more effectively and sustainably.

So it can be concluded that the use of the Bali Aga dialect in the work domain can bring many benefits, including increasing familiarity and efficiency of communication, as well as strengthening cultural identity. Despite indications of the use of other languages in some work contexts, the Bali Aga dialect remains the main medium of communication in local economic activities. This data confirms the strength and flexibility of the dialect in coping with the demands of modern communication in the work domain, while pointing to potential challenges in maintaining its use in the future as the economy develops and interacts with the outside world. Using the Bali Aga dialect shows respect for tradition and cultural heritage, which can be an important value in the work environment.

V. CONCLUSION

The research shows that the Bali Aga dialect still has a fairly high vitality in the work domain in Tigawasa Village. The Bali Aga dialect still has an important function as an identity marker, community unifier, and a means to preserve traditional knowledge in the context of work. The majority of residents still use the Bali Aga dialect as the main language in daily communication in the workplace, especially in traditional work and local economic activities. The people of Tigawasa Village have a positive attitude towards the use of the Bali Aga dialect in the work domain, although there is an awareness of the need for mastery of other languages for wider communication purposes. The Bali Aga dialect is predominantly used in informal interactions such as in weaving, farming and cattle raising activities. However, there is a tendency to use standard Indonesian or Balinese in formal situations or when interacting with outsiders or in official activities.

Supporting factors for the preservation of the Bali Aga dialect in Tigawasa Village support the preservation of the Bali Aga dialect in the work domain including:

- 1) The strong cultural identity of the Tigawasa community.
- 2) Relative isolation of the village that limits outside influence
- 3) Traditional economic activities that still survive
- 4) Ongoing intergenerational transmission.

There are indications that the Bali Aga dialect has adapted, especially in terms of vocabulary, to accommodate new concepts in the modern world of work. However, there are some challenges in the preservation of the Bali Aga dialect, including:

- 1) Modernization and the influx of new technology
- 2) Increased population mobility
- 3) The influence of media and formal education that uses Indonesian language. This research underscores the need for language

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policies that support the preservation of Bali Aga dialects, including the integration of dialects in education and local economic development. Despite facing various challenges, the Bali Aga dialect in Tigawasa Village has the potential to survive in the realm of work, especially if supported by preservation efforts involving all levels of society and related parties.

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